

Brownian Motion and Stochastic Calculus

Project Report

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Stochastic Calculus has found a wide range of applications in analyzing the evolution of many natural, but complex systems. In this project we discuss Brownian motion and Stochastic Calculus. In Stochastic Calculus, we focus on the topic of Itô integration. At the end, we study the existence and uniqueness problem for solutions of stochastic differential equation. Our main reference material are Mörters and Peres (2010) and Øksendal (1998).

In Chapter 2, we have listed preliminary notions about Stochastic Processes. In Chapter 3, we focus on the definition and properties of Brownian motion. In Chapter 4, we first discuss the construction of Itô integral and then look at the change of variables formula of Stochastic Calculus, the Itô formula. We finish with a discussion on existence and uniqueness problem for solutions of stochastic differential equation.

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

Definition 2.0.1 ((Øksendal, 1998, Def 2.1.4)). A stochastic process is a parametrized collection of random variables $\{X_t\}_{t \in T}$ defined on a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ and assuming values in \mathbb{R}^n .

The parameter space T can be any interval of the form $[a, b]$, the non-negative integers and even subsets of \mathbb{R}^n for $n \geq 1$. Note that for each $t \in T$ fixed we have a random variable

$$\omega \rightarrow X_t(\omega) ; \quad \omega \in \Omega.$$

On the other hand, fixing $\omega \in \Omega$ we can consider the function

$$t \rightarrow X_t(\omega) ; \quad t \in T$$

which is called a *path* of $\{X_t\}_t$.

We regard the process as a function of two variables

$$(t, \omega) \rightarrow X(t, \omega)$$

from $T \times \Omega$ into \mathbb{R}^n , thus it is crucial to have $X(t, \omega)$ jointly measurable in (t, ω) .

We may also associate each ω with the function $t \rightarrow X_t(\omega)$ from T into \mathbb{R}^n . Thus, we may regard Ω as a subset of the space $(\mathbb{R}^n)^T$ of all functions from T into \mathbb{R}^n . The σ -algebra \mathcal{F} will contain the σ -algebra \mathcal{B} generated by sets of the form

$$\{\omega : \omega(t_1) \in F_1, \dots, \omega(t_k) \in F_k\}, \quad F_i \subset \mathbb{R}^n \text{ Borel sets}$$

Therefore one may also adopt the point of view that a stochastic process is given by its law, which is a probability measure on the measurable space $((\mathbb{R}^n)^T, \mathcal{B})$.

Definition 2.0.2. The finite-dimensional distributions of the process $X = \{X_t\}_{t \in T}$ are

the measures $\mu_{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k}$ defined on \mathbb{R}^{nk} , $k = 1, 2, \dots$, by

$$\mu_{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k}(F_1 \times F_2 \times \dots \times F_k) = \mathbb{P}[X_{t_1} \in F_1, \dots, X_{t_k} \in F_k]; \quad t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k \in T.$$

Here F_1, \dots, F_k denote Borel sets in \mathbb{R}^n .

The family of all finite-dimensional distributions determine important properties of the process X . Conversely, given a family $\{\nu_{t_1, \dots, t_k}; k \in \mathbb{N}, t_i \in T\}$ of probability measures on \mathbb{R}^{nk} , it is possible to construct a stochastic process $Y = \{Y_t\}_{t \in T}$ having ν_{t_1, \dots, t_k} as its finite dimensional distributions under certain consistency conditions implied by the next theorem.

Theorem 2.0.3 ((Øksendal, 1998, Def 2.1.5) Kolmogorov Extension Theorem). *Let T be any interval. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and a finite sequence of distinct times $t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k \in T$, let $\nu_{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k}$ be a probability measure on \mathbb{R}^{nk} . Suppose these measures satisfy two consistency conditions:*

- For all permutations π of $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ and measurable sets $F_i \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\nu_{t_{\pi(1)}, t_{\pi(2)}, \dots, t_{\pi(k)}}(F_{\pi(1)} \times \dots \times F_{\pi(k)}) = \nu_{t_1, \dots, t_k}(F_1 \times \dots \times F_k)$$

- For all measurable sets $F_i \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\nu_{t_1, \dots, t_k}(F_1 \times \dots \times F_k) = \nu_{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k, t_{k+1}, \dots, t_{k+m}}(F_1 \times \dots \times F_k \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \dots \times \mathbb{R}^n)$$

This theorem guarantees that a suitably consistent collection of finite dimensional distributions will define a stochastic process.

Definition 2.0.4. Suppose that $\{X_t\}_t$ and $\{Y_t\}_t$ are stochastic processes on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$. Then we say that $\{X_t\}_t$ is a version of $\{Y_t\}_t$ if

$$\mathbb{P}(\{\omega : X_t(\omega) = Y_t(\omega)\}) = 1, \quad \forall t$$

Note that if $\{X_t\}_t$ is a version of $\{Y_t\}_t$, then they have the same finite dimensional distributions.

Also, $\{X_t\}_t$ is said to be indistinguishable from $\{Y_t\}_t$ if

$$\mathbb{P}(\{\omega : X_t(\omega) = Y_t(\omega); \forall t\}) = 1$$

Remark 2.0.5. Of course, it is obvious to see that if X and Y are indistinguishable, then X and Y are modifications of each other. The converse is not true in general. However, under certain conditions, if X and Y are modifications of each other then they are also indistinguishable. The conditions are listed as follows :

- i) If T is countable, if $\mathbb{P}(A_t) = 1$ for all $t \in T$, then $\mathbb{P}(\cap_{t \in T} A_t) = 1$ and vice-versa.
- ii) If X and Y are modifications of each other and are right continuous (or left continuous), then they are indistinguishable.

Proof. We only prove the case ii). Using the appropriate continuity hypothesis, we reduce the problem to a countable set of null sets. As such the subsequent argument remains the same for case i).

Since X and Y are modifications of each other, we have $\mathbb{P}(X_t \neq Y_t) = 0 \forall t \in T$. We define

$$\begin{aligned} A' &= \{\omega : X_t(\omega) = Y_t(\omega) \forall t \in T \cap \mathbb{Q}\} \\ &= \cap_{t \in T \cap \mathbb{Q}} \{\omega : X_t(\omega) = Y_t(\omega)\} \\ &= (\cup_{t \in T \cap \mathbb{Q}} \{\omega : X_t(\omega) \neq Y_t(\omega)\})^c \end{aligned}$$

As it is the complement of a countable union of sets having probability 0, we have $\mathbb{P}(A') = 1$. Set

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \{\omega : X(\omega) \text{ is right continuous}\} \\ C &= \{\omega : Y(\omega) \text{ is right continuous}\} \end{aligned}$$

By assumption, $\mathbb{P}(B) = \mathbb{P}(C) = 1$. Their intersection $A = A' \cap B \cap C$ is the collection of those paths which are right continuous and where the two processes agree on $T \cap \mathbb{Q}$. We have $\mathbb{P}(A) = 1$. Since $T \cap \mathbb{Q}$ is dense in T , we have for every $t \in T$, a sequence $\{q_n\} \subset T \cap \mathbb{Q}$ such that $q_n \rightarrow t^+$. Then using right continuity,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} X_{q_n}(\omega) = X_t(\omega)$$

and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Y_{q_n}(\omega) = Y_t(\omega)$$

for all $\omega \in A$. Again, since $X_{q_n}(\omega) = Y_{q_n}(\omega)$, we must have $X_t(\omega) = Y_t(\omega) \forall \omega \in A$. □

Theorem 2.0.6 ((Walsh, 1986, Theorem 1.1) Garcia, Rodemich, Rumsey (GRR) Inequality). *Let $\psi(x)$ and $p(x)$ be positive continuous functions on \mathbb{R} such that both ψ and p are symmetric about 0, $p(x)$ is increasing for $x > 0$ and $p(0) = 0$. Let ψ be convex with $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \psi(x) = \infty$. If R_1 is the unit cube in \mathbb{R}^n , and f is a measurable function on R_1 such that*

$$\int_{R_1} \int_{R_1} \psi \left(\frac{f(y) - f(x)}{p\left(\frac{|y-x|}{\sqrt{n}}\right)} \right) dx dy = B < \infty$$

then there is a set K of measure 0 such that if $x, y \in R_1 \setminus K$,

$$|f(y) - f(x)| \leq 8 \int_0^{|y-x|} \psi^{-1} \left(\frac{B}{u^{2n}} \right) dp(u) \quad (2.0.1)$$

If f is continuous, (2.0.1) holds for all x, y .

Proof. If R is a cube in \mathbb{R}^n , let $e(R)$ be the length of its edge and $|R|$ its volume. Let R_1 be the unit cube.

If $Q \subset R_1$ is a cube and $x, y \in Q$, then $|y - x| < \sqrt{n}e(Q)$. Also, ψ is increasing (as $\psi(x) = \psi(-x)$, ψ is convex and unbounded, then $\psi(x)$ is increasing on $[0, \infty)$). Hence,

$$\int_Q \int_Q \psi \left(\frac{f(y) - f(x)}{p(e(Q))} \right) dx dy \leq B$$

Let $Q_0 \supset Q_1 \supset \dots$ be a sequence of sub-cubes of R_1 such that

$$p(e(Q_j)) = \frac{1}{2}p(e(Q_{j-1}))$$

For any cube Q , let $f_Q = \frac{1}{|Q|} \int_Q f(x) dx$. Since ψ is convex,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \left(\frac{f_{Q_j} - f_{Q_{j-1}}}{p(e(Q_{j-1}))} \right) &\leq \frac{1}{|Q_{j-1}|} \int_{Q_{j-1}} \psi \left(\frac{f_{Q_j} - f(x)}{p(e(Q_{j-1}))} \right) dx \\ &\leq \frac{1}{|Q_{j-1}||Q_j|} \int_{Q_{j-1}} \int_{Q_j} \psi \left(\frac{f(y) - f(x)}{p(e(Q_{j-1}))} \right) dx dy \\ &\leq \frac{B}{|Q_{j-1}Q_j|} \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$|f_{Q_j} - f_{Q_{j-1}}| \leq p(e(Q_{j-1})) \psi^{-1} \left(\frac{B}{|Q_j||Q_{j-1}|} \right)$$

Again,

$$4|p(e(Q_{j+1})) - p(e(Q_j))| = p(e(Q_{j-1})) \quad (\text{as } p(e(Q_{j+1})) = \frac{1}{2}p(e(Q_j)))$$

Thus,

$$|f_{Q_j} - f_{Q_{j-1}}| \leq 4|p(e(Q_{j+1})) - p(e(Q_j))| \psi^{-1} \left(\frac{B}{|Q_j||Q_{j-1}|} \right)$$

Since ψ^{-1} is increasing, so if $e(Q_{j+1}) \leq u \leq e(Q_j)$, then

$$|Q_j||Q_{j-1}| \geq u^{2n}$$

and

$$\psi^{-1}\left(\frac{B}{|Q_j||Q_{j-1}|}\right) \leq \psi^{-1}\left(\frac{B}{u^{2n}}\right)$$

Set $v_j = e(Q_j)$, then

$$|f_{Q_j} - f_{Q_{j-1}}| \leq 4 \int_{v_j}^{v_{j-1}} \psi^{-1}\left(\frac{B}{u^{2n}}\right) dp(u)$$

Summing over all j , we have

$$\limsup |f_{Q_j} - f_{Q_0}| \leq 4 \int_0^{v_0} \psi^{-1}\left(\frac{B}{u^{2n}}\right) dp(u)$$

By Vitali's Theorem, if x is not in some null set K , then $f_{Q_j} \rightarrow f(x)$ for any sequence $\{Q_j\}$ of cubes decreasing to $\{x\}$. If $x, y \in R_1 \setminus K$ and take Q_0 to be the smallest cube containing both, then $v_0 \leq |y - x|$, which means,

$$|f(x) - f_{Q_0}| \leq 4 \int_0^{|y-x|} \psi^{-1}\left(\frac{B}{u^{2n}}\right) dp(u)$$

The same inequality holds true for y implying

$$|f(y) - f(x)| \leq 8 \int_0^{|y-x|} \psi^{-1}\left(\frac{B}{u^{2n}}\right) dp(u)$$

This completes the proof. □

We use the GRR inequality to prove the important result of Kolmogorov continuity.

Theorem 2.0.7 ((Walsh, 1986, Cor 1.2) Kolmogorov Continuity). *Let $\{X_t, t \in R_1\}$ be a real valued stochastic process. Suppose there are constants $k > 1, K > 0$ and $\epsilon > 0$ such that for all $s, t \in R_1$*

$$E[|X_t - X_s|^k] \leq K|t - s|^{n+\epsilon}$$

Then X has a continuous version.

Proof. We will apply the GRR Inequality to the paths of X . Replace x and y with s and t . The function $f(x)$ is replaced by the path $X_t(\omega)$ for a fixed ω . Choose $\psi(x) = |x|^k$ and $p(x) = |x|^{\frac{2n+\epsilon}{k}} \left(\log \frac{\gamma}{|x|}\right)^{\frac{2}{k}}$. If $\gamma = \sqrt{n}e^{\frac{k}{n}}$, $p(x)$ will be increasing on $(0, \sqrt{n})$. Since B is dependent on ω , it is now a random variable. By Fubini's theorem,

$$\begin{aligned} E(B) &= n^{n+\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \int_{R_1} \int_{R_1} \frac{E|X_t - X_s|^k}{|t - s|^{2n+\epsilon} \log^2\left(\frac{\gamma}{|t-s|}\right)} ds dt \\ &\leq n^{n+\frac{\epsilon}{2}} K \int_{R_1} \int_{R_1} \frac{ds dt}{|t - s|^n \log^2(\gamma|t - s|^{-1})} \end{aligned}$$

For a fixed t , the integral over R_1 w.r.t. s is dominated by the integral over the ball with radius \sqrt{n} centred at t . (since, the length of the diagonal of R_1 is \sqrt{n} and the ball contains R_1).

Let σ_n denote the area of the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^n . Using polar transformation, we write :

$$\begin{aligned} E(B) &\leq n^{n+\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \sigma_n K \int_0^{\sqrt{n}} \frac{r^{n-1} dr}{r^n (\log \frac{\gamma}{2})^2} \\ &= n^{n+1+\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \frac{\sigma_n}{k} K \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have $E(B) < \infty$, which implies $B < \infty$ a.s. Using the GRR inequality and integrating by parts twice, we have

$$|X_t - X_s| \leq 8B^{\frac{1}{k}} [|t-s|^{\frac{\epsilon}{k}} (\log \gamma |t-s|^{-1})^{\frac{2}{b}} (1 + \frac{2n}{\epsilon})] + \frac{4n}{k\epsilon} \int_0^{|t-s|} \log^{\frac{2}{k}-1}(\frac{\gamma}{u}) u^{\frac{\epsilon}{k}-1} du$$

The integral is dominated by $|t-s|^{\frac{\epsilon}{k}} (\log \gamma |t-s|^{-1})^{\frac{2}{k}}$ for small enough values of $|t-s|$ and for all $|t-s| \leq \sqrt{n}$ if $k \geq n$ so that for a real constant A , we have,

$$|X_t - X_s| \leq 8AB^{\frac{1}{k}} |t-s|^{\epsilon} k (\log \gamma |t-s|^{-1})^{\frac{2}{k}}$$

proving the claim. □

Definition 2.0.8 (Hölder Continuity). A function $f : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be locally α Hölder continuous at $x \geq 0$, if there exists $\epsilon > 0$ and $c > 0$ such that

$$|f(x) - f(y)| \leq c|x-y|^\alpha \text{ for all } y \geq 0 \text{ with } |y-x| < \epsilon$$

$\alpha > 0$ is said to be the Hölder exponent.

Definition 2.0.9 (Exchangeable events). Let X_1, X_2, \dots , be a sequence of random variables on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ and consider a set A of sequences such that

$$\{X_1, X_2, \dots \in A\} \in \mathcal{F}$$

The event $\{X_1, X_2, \dots \in A\}$ is called exchangeable if

$$\{X_1, X_2, \dots \in A\} \subset \{X_{\sigma_1}, X_{\sigma_2}, \dots \in A\}$$

for all finite permutations $\sigma : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

Theorem 2.0.10 (Hewitt-Savage 0 – 1 Law). *If E is an exchangeable event for an i.i.d sequence, $\mathbb{P}(E) = 0$ or 1*

Definition 2.0.11 ((Øksendal, 1998, Def 3.1.2)). Let $\{B_t\}_t$ be an n -dimensional Brownian Motion. Then we define \mathcal{F}_t to be the σ -algebra generated by the random variables $B_s(\cdot); s \leq t$. That is, \mathcal{F}_t is the smallest σ -algebra containing all sets of the form

$$\{\omega; B_{t_1}(\omega) \in F_1, \dots, B_{t_k}(\omega) \in F_k\}$$

where $t_j \leq t$ and $F_j \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are Borel sets, $j \leq k = 1, 2, \dots$

Remark 2.0.12. Observe that $\mathcal{F}_s \subset \mathcal{F}_t$ for $s < t$ and that $\mathcal{F}_t \subset \mathcal{F}$ for all t .

Definition 2.0.13 ((Øksendal, 1998, Def 3.1.3)). Let $\{\mathcal{N}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ be an increasing family of σ -algebras of subsets of Ω . A process $g(t, \omega) : [0, \infty) \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is called \mathcal{N}_t -adapted if for each $t \geq 0$ the function

$$\omega \rightarrow g(t, \omega)$$

is \mathcal{N}_t -measurable.

Definition 2.0.14 ((Øksendal, 1998, Def 3.2.2)). A filtration (on (Ω, \mathcal{F})) is a family $\mathcal{M} = \{\mathcal{M}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ of σ -algebras $\mathcal{M}_t \subset \mathcal{F}$ such that $0 \leq s \leq t$ implies $\mathcal{M}_s \subset \mathcal{M}_t$.

Definition 2.0.15. An n -dimensional stochastic process on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is called a **martingale** with respect to a filtration $\{\mathcal{M}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ and with respect to \mathbb{P} if :

- i) M_t is \mathcal{M}_t -measurable for all t
- ii) $E[|M_t|] < \infty$ for all t
- iii) $E[M_s | \mathcal{M}_t] = M_t$ for all $s \geq t$ a.s.

Theorem 2.0.16 ((Øksendal, 1998, Theorem 3.2.4) Doob's martingale inequality). *If M_t is a martingale such that $t \rightarrow M_t(\omega)$ is continuous a.s., then for all $p \geq 1$, $T \geq 0$ and all $\lambda > 0$*

$$\mathbb{P}\left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |M_t| \geq \lambda\right] \leq \frac{1}{\lambda^p} E[|M_T|^p]$$

Chapter 3

Brownian Motion, it's construction & properties

3.1 Introduction

In 1828, the Scottish botanist Robert Brown observed that pollen grains suspended in liquid performed an irregular motion. The motion was later explained by the random collisions with the molecules of the liquid. To describe the model mathematically, it is natural to use the idea of a stochastic process $\{B_t\}_t$, where $B_t(\omega)$ is interpreted as the position at time t of the pollen grain ω . We consider an n -dimensional analog.

Definition 3.1.1 (Mörters and Peres (2010)). A real valued stochastic process $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is called a **Brownian Motion** with start in $x \in \mathbb{R}$ if the following holds :

- $B_0 = x$
- The process has independent increments, that is for all n and for $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_n$, the increments $B_{t_n} - B_{t_{n-1}}, \dots, B_{t_2} - B_{t_1}, B_{t_1} - B_0$ are independent random variables.
- For all $t \geq 0$ and $h > 0$, the increments $B_{t+h} - B_t \sim N(0, h)$.
- Almost surely, the function $t \rightarrow B_t$ is continuous.

If $x = 0$, then we say that $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is a **Standard Brownian Motion**.

3.2 Construction

To construct $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$, we use the Kolmogorov Extension Theorem. Thus, it is sufficient to specify a family $\{\nu_{t_1, \dots, t_k}\}$ of probability measures satisfying the two consistency

conditions. Fix $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and define :

$$p(t, x, y) = (2\pi t)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \cdot \exp\left\{-\frac{|x-y|^2}{2t}\right\} \text{ for } y \in \mathbb{R}^n, t > 0$$

If $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_k$ we define a measure ν_{t_1, \dots, t_k} on \mathbb{R}^{nk} by

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{t_1, \dots, t_k}(F_1 \times F_2 \times \dots \times F_k) &= \int_{F_1 \times F_2 \times \dots \times F_k} p(t_1, x, x_1) \times p(t_2 - t_1, x_1, x_2) \times \dots \\ &\quad \times p(t_k - t_{k-1}, x_{k-1}, x_k) dx_1 \dots dx_k \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.1)$$

We use the convention that $p(0, x, y)dy = \delta_x(y)$, the unit point mass at x . Of course, we can extend this definition to all finite sequences of t_i 's by using the first consistency condition. Again since $\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p(t, x, y)dy = 1$ for all $t \geq 0$, the second consistency condition also holds true. So, by Kolmogorov's theorem there exists a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, P^x)$ and a stochastic process $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ on Ω such that the finite dimensional distributions of B_t are given by (2.2.1), that is

$$\begin{aligned} P^x(B_{t_1} \in F_1, \dots, B_{t_k} \in F_k) &= \int_{F_1 \times F_2 \times \dots \times F_k} p(t_1, x, x_1) \times p(t_2 - t_1, x_1, x_2) \times \dots \\ &\quad \times p(t_k - t_{k-1}, x_{k-1}, x_k) dx_1 \dots dx_k \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.2)$$

3.3 Properties

1. **A characterization of Brownian Motion**(Klenke, 2014, Theorem 21.11) : Let $X = \{X_t\}_t$ be a stochastic process with continuous paths and $X_0 = 0$ a.s. Then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) X is a Brownian Motion
- (ii) X is a centred Gaussian process with covariance $E(X_s X_t) = \min\{s, t\}$

Remark 3.3.1. X is called centred if $E(X_t) = 0, \forall t \in [0, \infty)$.

Proof. We first prove that Statement (i) implies Statement (ii).

Let $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_n$. By assumption, $X_{t_n} - X_{t_{n-1}}, \dots, X_{t_2} - X_{t_1}, X_{t_1}$ are independent Gaussian RVs. hence $(X_{t_1}, X_{t_2} - X_{t_1}, \dots, X_{t_n} - X_{t_{n-1}})$ is a Gaussian random vector and so is $(X_{t_1}, \dots, X_{t_n})$, as we have $(X_{t_1}, \dots, X_{t_n}) = A(X_{t_1}, X_{t_2} - X_{t_1}, \dots, X_{t_n} - X_{t_{n-1}})$ where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & & & & \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus X is a Gaussian process which is again centred.

Let us check the covariance of X . Let $t \geq s \geq 0$. We have $E(X_s X_t) = E(X_s(X_t - X_s)) + E(X_s^2)$. Since X_s and $X_t - X_s$ are independent, we have $E(X_s(X_t - X_s)) = 0$ and also by the properties of Brownian Motion, $E(X_s^2) = s$. Hence $E(X_s X_t) = s = \min\{s, t\}$.

Now, we go on to prove that Statement (ii) implies Statement (i).

Let $t \geq s \geq 0$. By assumption, $X_t - X_s$ is a centered Gaussian, with variance $E(X_t - X_s)^2 = E(X_t^2) + E(X_s^2) - 2E(X_t X_s) = t + s - 2s = t - s$. Thus the third property of Brownian Motion holds.

Let $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_n$. We know that $(X_{t_n} - X_{t_{n-1}}, \dots, X_{t_2} - X_{t_1}, X_{t_1})$ is a Gaussian random vector whose covariance matrix is diagonal. For $j > i$, $E[(X_{t_j} - X_{t_{j-1}})(X_{t_i} - X_{t_{i-1}})] = t_i - t_i - t_{i-1} + t_{i-1} = 0$. Thus the components of this Gaussian random vector are independent and hence the second property of Brownian Motion holds. \square

2. Scaling invariance(Mörters & Peres, 2010, Lemma 1.7) : Suppose $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is a Standard Brownian Motion and let $a > 0$. Then the process $\{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ defined by $X_t = \frac{1}{a}B_{a^2t}$ is also a Standard Brownian Motion.

Proof. Path continuity, independence and stationarity of increments remain unchanged under scaling. Now, $X_t - X_s = \frac{1}{a}(B_{a^2t} - B_{a^2s}) \sim N(0, \frac{1}{a^2}(a^2t - a^2s)) \equiv N(0, t - s)$. This completes the proof. \square

Remark 3.3.2. (Mörters & Peres, 2010, Remark 1.8) An useful consequence of scaling invariance is as follows. Let $a < 0 < b$. We now look at $T(a, b) = \inf\{t \geq 0 : B_t = a \text{ or } B_t = b\}$ which is also called the first exit time of a one-dimensional Standard Brownian Motion from the interval $[a, b]$. Then with $X_t = \frac{1}{a}B_{a^2t}$, we have $E(T(a, b)) = a^2E[\inf\{t \geq 0 : X_t = \frac{b}{a} \text{ or } X_t = 1\}] = a^2E[T(\frac{b}{a}, 1)]$. Plugging in $a = -b$, we have $E[T(-b, b)] = cb^2$ where c is a constant. Also, $P[\{B_t : t \geq 0\} \text{ exits } [a, b] \text{ at } b] = P[\{X_t : t \geq 0\} \text{ exits } [\frac{b}{a}, 1] \text{ at } 1]$ is only a function of the ratio $\frac{b}{a}$.

3. Time Inversion(Mörters & Peres, 2010, Theorem 1.9) : Suppose $\{B_t : t \geq 0\}$ is a Standard Brownian Motion. Then the process $\{X_t : t \geq 0\}$ defined by :

$$X(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t = 0 \\ tB_{\frac{1}{t}} & t > 0 \end{cases}$$

is also a Standard Brownian motion.

Proof. The finite dimensional distributions $(B_{t_1}, \dots, B_{t_n})$ of Brownian Motion are Gaussian random vectors and are characterized by $E(B_{t_i}) = 0$ and $\text{cov}(B_{t_i}, B_{t_j}) = t_i$ for $0 \leq t_i \leq t_j$. So, $\{X_t : t \geq 0\}$ is also a Gaussian process with the vector $(X_{t_1}, \dots, X_{t_n})$

having expectation 0 and covariance

$$\text{cov}(X_{t+h}, X_t) = (t+h)t \cdot \text{cov}(B_{\frac{1}{t+h}}, B_{\frac{1}{t}}) = t(t+h) \cdot \frac{1}{t+h} = t.$$

Thus, the law of all the finite dimensional distributions $(X_{t_1}, \dots, X_{t_n})$ for $0 \leq t_1 \leq \dots \leq t_n$ are the same as for Brownian Motion.

The paths of $t \rightarrow X_t$ are clearly continuous for all $t > 0$. Thus we need to check continuity at 0. To prove that we use the following two facts:

First, as the set \mathbb{Q} of rationals is countable, the distribution of $\{X_t : t \geq 0, t \in \mathbb{Q}\}$ is the same as for a Brownian Motion. This is because two stochastic processes have the same distribution iff all their finite dimensional distributions agree. Hence, $\lim_{\substack{t \downarrow 0 \\ t \in \mathbb{Q}}} X_t$ almost surely.

And second, $\mathbb{Q} \cap (0, \infty)$ is dense in $(0, \infty)$ and $\{X_t : t \geq 0\}$ is almost surely continuous on $(0, \infty)$, so that

$$0 = \lim_{\substack{t \downarrow 0 \\ t \in \mathbb{Q}}} X_t = \lim_{t \downarrow 0} X_t \quad a.s.$$

Hence, $\{X_t : t \geq 0\}$ has almost surely continuous paths and is a Brownian Motion. □

Remark 3.3.3. An useful consequence of time inversion is the Law of Large Numbers for a Brownian Motion. We have that almost surely, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_t}{t} = 0$.

Proof. Let $\{X_t : t \geq 0\}$ be the Brownian Motion as defined previously. By continuity at 0, $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} X_t = 0$ a.s. Putting $t = \frac{1}{u}$, we have $\lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_u}{u} = 0$ a.s.. □

Remark 3.3.4. For a one-dimensional Brownian Motion $\{B_t\}_t$, it can be shown easily that

$$E(|B_t - B_s|^4) = 3|t - s|^2$$

Thus, the Kolmogorov continuity criterion is satisfied for this case with $n = 1, \epsilon = 1, k = 4$ and $K = 3$. This implies that B_t has a **continuous version**.

4. **Hölder continuity:** (Mörters & Peres, 2010, Cor 1.20) If $\alpha < \frac{1}{2}$, then almost surely, Brownian motion is everywhere locally α -Holder continuous.

Lemma 3.3.5 ((Mörters & Peres, 2010, Theorem 1.12)). *There exists a constant $C > 0$ such that, almost surely, for every sufficiently small $h > 0$ and all $0 \leq t \leq 1 - h$,*

$$|B_{t+h} - B_t| \leq C \sqrt{h \log\left(\frac{1}{h}\right)}$$

Proof. We use the construction of Brownian Motion on $[0, 1]$. Let $D_n = \{\frac{k}{2^n} : 0 \leq k \leq 2^n\}$ and $D = \cup_{n=0}^{\infty} D_n$. Consider $\{Z_t\}_{t \in D}$ to be a collection of independent standard normal

random variables. Let

$$F_0(t) = \begin{cases} Z_1, & t = 1 \\ 0, & t = 0 \\ \text{defined linearly in between} \end{cases}$$

For $n \geq 1$,

$$F_n(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{-\frac{(n+1)}{2}} Z_t, & t \in D_n \setminus D_{n-1} \\ 0, & t \in D_{n-1} \\ \text{defined linearly in between} \end{cases}$$

Thus, we can write $B_t = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_n(t)$. Here F_n is a piece-wise linear function. The derivative of F_n exists almost everywhere by definition and for any $C > \sqrt{2 \log 2}$, there exists a random $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n > N$,

$$\|F'_n\|_{\infty} \leq \frac{2\|F_n\|_{\infty}}{2^{-n}} \leq 2C\sqrt{n}2^{\frac{n}{2}} \quad (3.3.1)$$

Now for each $t, t+h \in [0, 1]$,

$$|B_{t+h} - B_t| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |F_n(t+h) - F_n(t)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^l \|F'_n\|_{\infty} h + \sum_{n=l+1}^{\infty} 2\|F_n\|_{\infty}$$

Also, $\|F_n\|_{\infty} < C\sqrt{n}2^{-\frac{n}{2}}$. Thus for all $l > N$,

$$|B_{t+h} - B_t| \leq h \sum_{n=0}^N \|F'_n\|_{\infty} + 2Ch \sum_{n=N}^l \sqrt{n}2^{\frac{n}{2}} + 2C \sum_{n=l+1}^{\infty} \sqrt{n}2^{-\frac{n}{2}}$$

We can take h to be small enough that the first summand $\leq \sqrt{h \log(\frac{1}{h})}$ and l such that $2^{-l} < h \leq 2^{-l+1}$ and $l > N$. For this choice of l , the second and third summands are bounded above by constant multiples of $\sqrt{h \log(\frac{1}{h})}$. Thus,

$$|B_{t+h} - B_t| \leq C\sqrt{h \log\left(\frac{1}{h}\right)}$$

□

. Proof of Hölder continuity] Using the above lemma on Brownian Motions $\{B_t - B_k : t \in [k, k+1]\}$ where k is a non-negative integer, we see that a.s. for every k , there exists

$h(k) > 0$ such that $\forall t \in [k, k+1)$ and $h \in (0, \min\{h(k), k+1-t\})$,

$$|B_{t+h} - B_t| \leq C \sqrt{h \log\left(\frac{1}{h}\right)} \leq Ch^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{h}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}-\alpha} = Ch^\alpha$$

With the same argument for the Brownian motions $\{\tilde{B}_t : t \in [k, k+1]\}$ with $\tilde{B}_t = B_{k+1-t} - B_{k+1}$, we have the full result. \square

5. Non-monotonicity:(Mörters & Peres, 2010, Theorem 1.22) Almost surely, for all $0 < a < b < \infty$, the standard Brownian Motion is not monotone on the interval $[a, b]$.

Proof. It suffices to look at intervals with rational endpoints because any general non-degenerate interval of monotonicity must contain one such interval. Since there are countably many rational intervals, it suffices to prove that any particular one has probability 0 of being monotone. Let $[a, b]$ be such an interval. Note that for any finite partition $a = a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{n-1} < a_n = b$, the probability that $B_{a_i} - B_{a_{i-1}}$ is either ≥ 0 or ≤ 0 for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ is $2 \cdot \frac{1}{2^n}$ by the symmetry of the Gaussian distribution. This probability approaches 0 as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, a.s. there is no nondegenerate interval of monotonicity with rational endpoints. Now we can write any interval as a countable union of those and hence we are done. \square

6. Non-differentiability(Mörters & Peres, 2010, Prop 1.23) We first state the following lemma:

Lemma 3.3.6. *Almost surely,*

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{\sqrt{n}} = \infty$$

and

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{\sqrt{n}} = -\infty$$

Proof. By reverse Fatou's lemma,

$$\begin{aligned} P\{B_n > c\sqrt{n} \text{ i.o.}\} &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} P\{B_n > c\sqrt{n}\} \\ &= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} P\{B_1 > c\} > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Let $X_n = B_n - B_{n-1}$. Note that,

$$\{B_n > c\sqrt{n} \text{ i.o.}\} = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n X_j > c\sqrt{n} \text{ i.o.} \right\}$$

is an exchangeable event. Hence by 0 – 1 law,

$$P[B_n > c\sqrt{n} \text{ i.o.}] = 1$$

Taking the intersection over all positive integers c , we have a.s.

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{\sqrt{n}} = \infty$$

The second part can be proved by a similar argument. \square

Definition 3.3.7. For a function f , we define the upper and lower right derivatives as,

$$D^*f(t) = \limsup_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(t+h) - f(t)}{h}$$

and

$$D_*f(t) = \liminf_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(t+h) - f(t)}{h}$$

Theorem 3.3.8 ((Mörters & Peres, 2010, Theorem 1.27)). *Fix $t \geq 0$. Then almost surely, Brownian Motion is not differentiable at t . Moreover, a.s. $D^*B_t = \infty$ and $D_*B_t = -\infty$.*

Proof. Consider

$$X_t = \begin{cases} 0; & t = 0 \\ tB_{\frac{1}{t}}; & t > 0 \end{cases}$$

Then a.s.

$$D^*X_0 \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{X_{\frac{1}{n}} - X_0}{\frac{1}{n}} \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{n}X_{\frac{1}{n}} \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{\sqrt{n}} = \infty$$

Similarly, a.s. $D_*X_0 = -\infty$. Thus X is not differentiable at 0. Again, it is to be noted that $X_s = B_{t+s} - B_s$ is a standard Brownian Motion (time shift invariance) and checking differentiability of X at 0 is equivalent to checking differentiability of B at t . \square

In fact, we can prove something much stronger.

Theorem 3.3.9 ((Mörters & Peres, 2010, Theorem 1.30)). *Almost surely, Brownian Motion is nowhere differentiable. Furthermore, almost surely for all t ,*

$$D^*B_t = \infty$$

or

$$D_*B_t = -\infty$$

or both.

Proof. Suppose that there is a $t_0 \in [0, 1]$ such that $-\infty < D_* B_{t_0} \leq D^* B_{t_0} < \infty$. Then,

$$\limsup_{h \downarrow 0} \frac{|B_{t_0+h} - B_{t_0}|}{h} < \infty$$

and since Brownian Motion is bounded on $[0, 2]$ we have for $M < \infty$, there exists t_0 with

$$\sup_{h \in [0, 1]} \frac{|B_{t_0+h} - B_{t_0}|}{h} \leq M$$

It suffices to show that this event has probability 0 for any M . So, first let us fix M .

If $t_0 \in [\frac{k-1}{2^n}, \frac{k}{2^n}]$ for $n > 2$, then for all $j \in [1, 2^n - k]$, the triangle inequality gives us :

$$\begin{aligned} \left| B_{\frac{k+j}{2^n}} - B_{\frac{k+j-1}{2^n}} \right| &\leq \left| B_{\frac{k+j}{2^n}} - B_{t_0} \right| + \left| B_{t_0} - B_{\frac{k+j-1}{2^n}} \right| \\ &\leq \frac{M(2j+1)}{2^n} \end{aligned}$$

Define the events

$$\Omega_{n,k} = \left\{ \left| B_{\frac{k+j}{2^n}} - B_{\frac{k+j-1}{2^n}} \right| \leq \frac{M(2j+1)}{2^n} \text{ for } j = 1, 2, 3 \right\}$$

Then by the independence of increments,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}[\Omega_{n,k}] &= \prod_{j=1}^3 \mathbb{P} \left[\left| B_{\frac{k+j}{2^n}} - B_{\frac{k+j-1}{2^n}} \right| \leq \frac{M(2j+1)}{2^n} \right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{P} \left[|B_{2^{-n}}| \leq \frac{7M}{2^n} \right]^3 \\ &= \mathbb{P} \left[\left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^{-n}}} B_{[\sqrt{2^{-n}}]^2} \right| \leq \frac{7M}{\sqrt{2^{-n}} 2^n} \right]^3 \\ &= \mathbb{P} \left[|B_1| \leq \frac{7M}{\sqrt{2^n}} \right]^3 \\ &\leq \left(\int_{-7M2^{-\frac{n}{2}}}^{7M2^{-\frac{n}{2}}} \frac{1}{2} dt \right)^3 \\ &= (7M2^{-\frac{n}{2}})^3 \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have :

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{2^n-3} \Omega_{n,k} \right) \leq (2^n - 3)(7M2^{-\frac{n}{2}})^3 \leq 2^n (7M2^{-\frac{n}{2}})^3 = 7M^3 2^{-\frac{n}{2}}$$

As $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2^{-\frac{n}{2}} < \infty$, by Borel-Cantelli lemma,

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{2^n-3} \Omega_{n,k} \text{ for infinitely many } n \right) = 0$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{P} \left\{ \text{there is } t_0 \in [0, 1] \text{ with } \sup_{h \in [0,1]} \frac{|B_{t_0+h} - B_{t_0}|}{h} \leq M \right\} \\ & \leq \mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{2^n-3} \Omega_{n,k} \text{ for infinitely many } n \right) \\ & = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Taking countable unions over all $M \in \mathbb{N}$ and intervals $[i, i + 1], i \in \mathbb{N}$, the proof is completed. \square

Chapter 4

Construction and properties of the Itô Integral

4.1 Motivation behind Stochastic Differential Equations

If we try to track the movement of a particle in a non-homogeneous medium, we encounter equations of the form :

$$dX_t = b(t, X_t).dt + \sigma(t, X_t)dW_t$$

where b, σ are some given functions. Here $\{W_t\}_t$ is an one-dimensional stochastic process representing the noise term.

To re-write the equation in its discrete version, let $0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_m = t$. Then ,

$$X_{k+1} - X_k = b(t_k, X_k)\Delta t_k + \sigma(t_k, X_k)W_k\Delta t_k$$

where $X_j = X(t_j)$, $W_k = W_{t_k}$, $\Delta t_k = t_{k+1} - t_k$.

We replace $W_k\Delta t_k$ by $\Delta V_k = V_{t_{k+1}} - V_{t_k}$, where $\{V_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is some suitable stochastic process. Now if we try to impose certain assumptions of independence and stationarity on W_t , we have that V_t should have stationary independent increments with mean 0. From our discussion in Chapter 2, we conclude that only such process with continuous paths is the Brownian Motion $\{B_t\}$. Thus we plug in $V_t = B_t$ and obtain:

$$X_k = X_0 + \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} b(t_j, X_j)\Delta t_j + \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sigma(t_j, X_j)\Delta B_j$$

If the limit of the RHS exists as $\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$, then by applying the usual integration notation, formally we write :

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t b(s, X_s) ds + \int_0^t \sigma(s, X_s) dB_s$$

To make sense of this equation, we shall discuss an appropriate construction of the integral :

$$\int_0^t f(s, \omega) dB_s(\omega)$$

where $\{B_t\}_t$ is an one-dimensional Brownian Motion starting at the origin.

Choose time points $0 \leq S < T$ and let $f : [0, \infty) \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be given. We want to define :

$$\int_S^T f(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega)$$

We start with a definition for a simple class of functions f and then extend by approximation. Let us assume that f has the form :

$$\phi(t, \omega) = \sum_{j \geq 0} e_j(\omega) \mathbb{1}_{[j \cdot 2^{-n}, (j+1) \cdot 2^{-n})}(t)$$

For such functions, it is reasonable to define :

$$\int_S^T \phi(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega) = \sum_{j \geq 0} e_j(\omega) [B_{t_{j+1}} - B_{t_j}](\omega)$$

where

$$t_k = \begin{cases} k \cdot 2^{-n} & \text{if } S \leq k \cdot 2^{-n} \leq T \\ S & \text{if } k \cdot 2^{-n} < S \\ T & \text{if } k \cdot 2^{-n} > T \end{cases}$$

However, we will see later that we need to make further assumptions on the functions $e_j(\omega)$, otherwise we will land up in difficulties.

In general, it is natural to approximate $f(t, \omega)$ by

$$\sum_j f(t_j^*, \omega) \mathbb{1}_{[t_j, t_{j+1})}(t)$$

where $t_j^* \in [t_j, t_{j+1}]$, and then define $\int_S^T f(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega)$ as the limit of

$$\sum_j f(t_j^*, \omega) [B_{t_{j+1}} - B_{t_j}](\omega)$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

However, it is to be noted that unlike the Riemann-Stieltjes integral, it does matter what points t_j^* are chosen. Two choices which have turned out to be the most useful ones :

- $t_j^* = t_j$, which leads to the **Itô integral** denoted by :

$$\int_S^T f(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega)$$

- $t_j^* = \frac{t_j + t_{j+1}}{2}$, which leads to the **Stratonovich Integral** denoted by :

$$\int_S^T f(t, \omega) \circ dB_t(\omega)$$

We will work with Itô's choice of $t_j^* = t_j$. The approximation procedure indicated above will work out successfully provided that f has the property that each of the functions $\omega \rightarrow f(t_j, \omega)$ only depends on the behaviour of $B_s(\omega)$ upto time t_j .

4.2 Constructing the Itô Integral

First of all, let us define the following class of functions :

Definition 4.2.1 ((Øksendal, 1998, Definition 3.1.4)). Let $V = V(S, T)$ be the class of functions

$$f(t, \omega) : [0, \infty) \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

such that :

- $(t, \omega) \rightarrow f(t, \omega)$ is $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{F}$ measurable, where \mathcal{B} denotes the Borel σ -algebra on $[0, \infty)$
- $f(t, \omega)$ is \mathcal{F}_t - adapted.
- $E[\int_S^T f(t, \omega)^2 dB_t(\omega)] < \infty$

For functions $f \in V$, we are interested in defining the Itô integral

$$I[f](\omega) = \int_S^T f(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega)$$

The idea is to first define $I[\phi]$ for elementary functions ϕ . Then we show that each $f \in V$ can be approximated by such ϕ 's and we use this to define $\int f dB$ as the limit of $\int \phi dB$ as $\phi \rightarrow f$.

Definition 4.2.2. A function $\phi \in V$ is called elementary if it has the form

$$\phi(t, \omega) = \sum_j e_j(\omega) \mathbb{1}_{[t_j, t_{j+1})}(\omega)$$

Since $\phi \in V$, each function e_j must be \mathcal{F}_{t_j} -measurable. For elementary functions $\phi(t, \omega)$ we define the integral :

$$\int_S^T \phi(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega) = \sum_{j \geq 0} e_j(\omega) [B_{t_{j+1}} - B_{t_j}](\omega)$$

Lemma 4.2.3 ((Øksendal, 1998, 3.1.5) Itô isometry). *If $\phi(t, \omega)$ is bounded and elementary, then*

$$E\left[\left(\int_S^T \phi(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega)\right)^2\right] = E\left[\int_S^T \phi(t, \omega)^2 dt\right]$$

Proof. Let $\Delta B_j = B_{t_{j+1}} - B_{t_j}$. Note that for every i , $\mathcal{F}_i = \sigma(B_s, s \leq t_i)$ we have each ΔB_i is independent of \mathcal{F}_i and ΔB_i is \mathcal{F}_{i+1} measurable.

For $i < j$,

$$E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i \Delta B_j] = E[E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i \Delta B_j | \mathcal{F}_{t_j}]]$$

Here we use the fact that for $i < j$ we have $\mathcal{F}_{t_i} \subset \mathcal{F}_{t_j}$

By hypothesis, e_i is \mathcal{F}_{t_i} measurable and hence is \mathcal{F}_{t_j} measurable. Thus, $e_i, e_j, \Delta B_i$ are all \mathcal{F}_{t_j} measurable and ΔB_j is independent of \mathcal{F}_{t_j} . Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} E[E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i \Delta B_j | \mathcal{F}_{t_j}]] &= E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i E[\Delta B_j | \mathcal{F}_{t_j}]] \\ &= E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i E[\Delta B_j]] \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i \Delta B_j] = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \\ E(e_j^2)(t_{j+1} - t_j) & \text{if } i = j \end{cases}$$

Finally, observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi^2 &= \left(\sum_j e_j \mathbb{1}_{I_j}\right)^2 \quad \text{where } I_j = [t_j, t_{j+1}) \\ &= \sum_j e_j \mathbb{1}_{I_j} \sum_k e_k \mathbb{1}_{I_k} \\ &= \sum_j e_j^2 \mathbb{1}_{I_j} \quad \text{as the intervals } I_j \& I_k \text{ are disjoint for } j \neq k \end{aligned}$$

which gives us :

$$E\left[\left(\int_S^T \phi dB\right)^2\right] = \sum_{i,j} E[e_i e_j \Delta B_i \Delta B_j]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_j E[e_j^2] \cdot (t_{j+1} - t_j) \\
&= E \left[\int_S^T \phi^2 dt \right]
\end{aligned}$$

□

We use this isometry to extend the definition of Itô integrals from elementary functions to functions in V . We do that in three steps :

Step 1. Let $g \in V$ be bounded and $g(\cdot, \omega)$ continuous for each ω . Then there exists elementary functions $\phi_n \in V$ such that

$$E \left[\int_S^T (g - \phi_n)^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof of existence of such functions. Define $\phi_n(t, \omega) = \sum_j g(t_j, \omega) \mathbb{1}_{[t_j, t_{j+1})}(t)$.

Since $g \in V$, ϕ_n is elementary. We have $t_j = \frac{j}{2^n}$. We already know that if $f : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function and $f_n(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} f(t_j) \mathbb{1}_{[t_j, t_{j+1})}(t)$, with $t_j = \frac{j}{2^n}$, then $f_n(t) \rightarrow f(t)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for all $t \geq 0$.

Applying this result for each fixed ω , we get

$$\phi_n(t, \omega) \rightarrow g(t, \omega) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Moreover,

$$|\phi_n(t, \omega) - g(t, \omega)| \leq |\phi_n(t, \omega)| + |g(t, \omega)| \leq 2\|g\|_{\infty} < \infty$$

By Dominated Convergence Theorem,

$$E \left[\int_S^T (g - \phi_n)^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

□

Step 2. Let $h \in V$ be bounded. Then there exists bounded functions $g_n \in V$ such that $g_n(\cdot, \omega)$ is continuous for all ω and n and

$$E \left[\int_S^T (h - g_n)^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof of existence of such functions. Suppose $|h(t, \omega)| \leq M$ for all (t, ω) . For each n , let ψ_n be a non-negative, continuous function on \mathbb{R} such that,

i) $\psi_n(x) = 0$ for $x \leq -\frac{1}{n}$ and $x \geq 0$

ii) $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_n(x) dx = 1$

Define

$$g_n(t, \omega) = \int_0^t \psi_n(s-t)h(s, \omega)ds$$

$g_n(t, \omega)$ is continuous for each ω as it is a convolution and inherits continuity from ψ_n .

Also, $|g_n(t, \omega)| \leq M$.

Since $h \in V$, it can be shown that $g_n(t, \cdot)$ is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable.

Again ψ_n constitutes an **approximate identity**. Thus

$$\int_S^T (g_n(s, \omega) - h(s, \omega))^2 ds \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \text{ for each } \omega$$

By Dominated Convergence Theorem,

$$E \left[\int_S^T (h(t, \omega) - g_n(t, \omega))^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

□

Step 3. Let $f \in V$. Then there exists functions $h_n \in V$ such that h_n is bounded for each n and

$$E \left[\int_S^T (f - h_n)^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof of existence of such functions. We take

$$h_n(t, \omega) = \begin{cases} -n & \text{if } f(t, \omega) < -n \\ f(t, \omega) & \text{if } |f(t, \omega)| \leq n \\ n & \text{if } f(t, \omega) > n \end{cases}$$

Then h_n is bounded for each n . Again, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we can conclude the result. □

We are now ready to complete the definition of the Itô integral

$$\int_S^T f(t, \omega)dB_t(\omega) \text{ for } f \in V.$$

Using steps 1-3, we choose elementary functions $\phi_n \in V$ such that

$$E \left[\int_S^T |f - \phi_n|^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0$$

Then define

$$I[f](\omega) := \int_S^T f(t, \omega)dB_t(\omega) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_S^T \phi_n(t, \omega)dB_t(\omega)$$

To show the well-definedness, we use the following reasoning via the triangle inequality. Fix some function $f \in V$. By step 3, $\exists h_n$ with

$$\sqrt{E \int_S^T (f - h_n)^2 dt} \leq \frac{1}{3n}$$

By step 2, $\exists g_n$ with

$$\sqrt{E \int_S^T (h_n - g_n)^2 dt} \leq \frac{1}{3n}$$

and finally by step 1, there is a ϕ_n with

$$\sqrt{E \int_S^T (g_n - \phi_n)^2 dt} \leq \frac{1}{3n}$$

Since $\sqrt{E \int_S^T f(t)^2 dt}$ is a norm (the L^2 norm with respect to the product measure $\mathbb{P} \otimes \lambda$). Hence, we have by the triangle inequality :

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{E \int_S^T (f - \phi_n)^2 dt} &\leq \sqrt{E \int_S^T (f - h_n)^2 dt} + \sqrt{E \int_S^T (h_n - g_n)^2 dt} + \sqrt{E \int_S^T (g_n - \phi_n)^2 dt} \\ &\leq 3 \cdot \frac{1}{3n} = \frac{1}{n} \end{aligned}$$

This allows us to conclude the above mentioned limit.

It is to be noted that the limit exists as an element of $L^2(\mathbb{P})$ because of the fact that $\{\int_S^T \phi_n(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega)\}_n$ forms a Cauchy sequence in $L^2(\mathbb{P})$. This fact is established as follows.

Proof. Take $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n > m$,

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\int_S^T |\phi_n(t) - \phi_m(t)|^2 dt \right] &= E \left[\int_S^T |\phi_n(t) - f(t) + f(t) - \phi_m(t)|^2 dt \right] \\ &\leq E \left[\int_S^T (2|\phi_n(t) - f(t)|^2 + 2|f(t) - \phi_m(t)|^2) dt \right] \\ &= 2E \left[\int_S^T |\phi_n(t) - f(t)|^2 dt \right] + 2E \left[\int_S^T |f(t) - \phi_m(t)|^2 dt \right] \\ &\xrightarrow{n, m \rightarrow \infty} 0 \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$E \left| \int_S^T \phi_n(t) dB_t - \int_S^T \phi_m(t) dB_t \right|^2 = E \left| \int_S^T (\phi_n(t) - \phi_m(t)) dB_t \right|^2$$

$$= E \left[\int_S^T |\phi_n(t) - \phi_m(t)|^2 dB_t \right] \xrightarrow{n,m \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

The last equality is due to Itô isometry. □

Remark 4.2.4. For all $f \in V(S, T)$, we have :

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\left(\int_S^T f(t, \omega) dB_t \right)^2 \right] &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E \left[\left(\int_S^T \phi_n(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega) \right)^2 \right] \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E \left[\int_S^T \phi_n^2(t, \omega) dt \right] \\ &= E \left[\int_S^T f^2(t, \omega) dt \right] \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4.2.5 ((Øksendal, 1998, Cor 3.1.8)). *If $f(t, \omega) \in V(S, T)$, $f_n(t, \omega) \in V(S, T)$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$ and $E[\int_S^T (f_n(t, \omega) - f(t, \omega))^2 dt] \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then*

$$\int_S^T f_n(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega) \longrightarrow \int_S^T f(t, \omega) dB_t(\omega) \text{ in } L^2(\mathbb{P}) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

4.2.1 A comparison of Itô and Stratonovich Integrals

Take a standard Brownian Motion $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$. We first calculate the Itô integral

$$\int_0^T B_s dB_s$$

We put $\phi_n(s, \omega) = \sum_{j \geq 0} B_j(\omega) \mathbb{1}_{[t_j, t_{j+1})}(s)$. Here we set $B_j = B_{t_j}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\int_0^T (\phi_n - B_s)^2 ds \right] &= E \left[\sum_j \int_{t_j}^{t_{j+1}} (B_j - B_s)^2 ds \right] \\ &= \sum_j \int_{t_j}^{t_{j+1}} (s - t_j) ds \\ &= \sum_j \frac{1}{2} (t_{j+1} - t_j)^2 \\ &\leq \frac{T}{2} \sum_j (t_{j+1} - t_j) \\ &\leq \frac{T}{2} |\Pi|, \text{ where } \Pi \text{ is the mesh size of the partition} \\ &\longrightarrow 0 \text{ as } |\Pi| \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}\int_0^T B_s dB_s &= \lim_{\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0} \int_0^T \phi_n dB_s \\ &= \lim_{\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0} \sum_j B_j \Delta B_j\end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\Delta B_j^2 = B_{j+1}^2 - B_j^2 = (\Delta B_j)^2 + 2B_j \Delta B_j$$

This leads to :

$$B_T^2 = \sum_j \Delta B_j^2 = \sum_j (\Delta B_j)^2 + 2 \sum_j B_j \Delta B_j$$

Thus, finally we have :

$$\sum_j B_j \Delta B_j = \frac{1}{2} B_T^2 - \frac{1}{2} (\Delta B_j)^2 \quad (4.2.1)$$

Now, as $\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$, $\sum_j (\Delta B_j)^2 \rightarrow T$ in $L^2(\mathbb{P})$, as the quadratic variation of a standard Brownian Motion on any interval $[0, T]$ is $T - 0 = T$. Thus, taking $\lim_{\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0}$ on both sides of (4.2.1), we have

$$\int_0^T B_s dB_s = \frac{1}{2} B_T^2 - \frac{T}{2} \quad (4.2.2)$$

Now, let us compute the same integral using Stratonovich's definition : that is, we aim to compute

$$\int_0^T B_t \circ dB_t$$

It is to be noted that

$$\begin{aligned}B_T^2 &= \sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_j}^2 - B_{t_{j-1}}^2) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n ((B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*}) + B_{t_j^*})^2 - ((B_{t_{j-1}} - B_{t_j^*}) + B_{t_j^*})^2 \\ &= 2 \sum_{j=1}^n B_{t_j^*} (B_{t_j} - B_{t_{j-1}}) + \sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*})^2 - \sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_{j-1}} - B_{t_j^*})^2\end{aligned}$$

where $t_j^* = \frac{t_j + t_{j-1}}{2}$.

The first term on the RHS that is, $\sum_{j=1}^n B_{t_j^*} (B_{t_j} - B_{t_{j-1}})$ converges to the Stratonovich integral $\int_0^T B_t \circ dB_t$ by definition.

We now show that the remaining terms converge to 0 as the mesh size $|\Pi| \rightarrow 0$. We set $S_n := \sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*})^2$ and $E(S_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n (t_j - t_j^*) = \frac{T}{2}$.

So, we get

$$E \left[\sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*})^2 \right] = V(S_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n V \left[(B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*})^2 - (t_j - t_j^*) \right]$$

Using scaling invariance, B_t has the same distribution as $\sqrt{t}B_1$ for any $t \geq 0$. We find that,

$$E \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*})^2 - \frac{T}{2} \right)^2 \right] \leq C |\Pi| T \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } |\Pi| \rightarrow 0$$

for $C := E((B_1^2 - 1)^2) < \infty$.

Thus,

$$\sum_{j=1}^n (B_{t_j} - B_{t_j^*})^2 \xrightarrow{L^2(\mathbb{P})} \frac{T}{2}$$

Exactly the same calculation goes through for the third addend. Finally,

$$B_T^2 = 2 \int_0^T B_t \circ dB_t + \frac{T}{2} - \frac{T}{2}$$

This implies

$$\frac{1}{2} B_T^2 = \int_0^T B_t \circ dB_t \tag{4.2.3}$$

Hence, we see from the equations (4.2.2) and (4.2.3) that the Itô and Stratonovich integrals disagree for the same integrand.

4.2.2 Continuous Version of the Ito Integral

We now use the Doob's Martingale inequality to prove that the Ito integral can be chosen to depend continuously on t .

Theorem 4.2.6 ((Øksendal, 1998, Cor 3.2.5)). *Let $f \in V(0, T)$. Then there exists a t -continuous version of $\int_0^t f(s, \omega) dB_s(\omega)$ for $0 \leq t \leq T$.*

Proof. Let $\phi_n = \phi_n(t, \omega) = \sum_j e_j^{(n)}(\omega) \mathbb{1}_{[t_j^{(n)}, t_{j+1}^{(n)})}$ elementary functions such that

$$E \left[\int_0^T (f - \phi_n)^2 dt \right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ when } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Put $I_n(t, \omega) = \int_0^t \phi_n(s, \omega) dB_s(\omega)$ and $I_t = I(t, \omega) = \int_0^t f(s, \omega) dB_s(\omega)$; $0 \leq t \leq T$.

Then, $I_n(\cdot, \omega)$ is continuous for all n . This is because of the fact that :

$$I_n(t) = \sum_{j=1}^n e_j(\omega) (B_{t_{j+1}^{(n)}}(\omega) - B_{t_j^{(n)}}(\omega))$$

which is continuous in t as $t \rightarrow B_t(\omega)$ is continuous.

Moreover, $I_n(t, \omega)$ is a martingale with respect to \mathcal{F}_t . Thus, for all n , when $t < s$: a.s.

$$\begin{aligned}
E[I_n(s, \omega) | \mathcal{F}_t] &= E \left[\left(\int_0^t \phi_n dB + \int_t^s \phi_n dB \right) | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \\
&= \int_0^t \phi_n dB + E \left[\sum_{t \leq t_j^{(n)} \leq t_{j+1}^{(n)} \leq s} e_j^{(n)} \Delta B_j | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \\
&= \int_0^t \phi_n dB + \sum_j E[E[e_j^{(n)} \Delta B_j | \mathcal{F}_{t_j^{(n)}}] | \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= \int_0^t \phi_n dB + \sum_j E[e_j^{(n)} E[\Delta B_j | \mathcal{F}_{t_j^{(n)}}] | \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= \int_0^t \phi_n dB = I_n(t, \omega)
\end{aligned}$$

Again $I_n - I_m$ is an \mathcal{F}_t - martingale, so by Doob's martingale inequality :

$$\begin{aligned}
P \left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |I_n(t, \omega) - I_m(t, \omega)| > \epsilon \right] &\leq \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} E[|I_n(T, \omega) - I_m(T, \omega)|^2] \\
&= \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} E \left[\int_0^T (\phi_n - \phi_m)^2 ds \right] \rightarrow 0 \\
&\text{as } m, n \rightarrow \infty
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we may choose a sub-sequence $n_k \uparrow \infty$ such that

$$P \left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |I_{n_{k+1}}(t, \omega) - I_{n_k}(t, \omega)| > 2^{-k} \right] < 2^{-k}$$

By the Borel-Cantelli lemma,

$$P \left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |I_{n_{k+1}}(t, \omega) - I_{n_k}(t, \omega)| > 2^{-k} \text{ for infinitely many } k \right] = 0$$

So, for almost all ω , there exists $k_1(\omega)$ such that

$$\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |I_{n_{k+1}}(t, \omega) - I_{n_k}(t, \omega)| \leq 2^{-k} \text{ for } k \geq k_1(\omega)$$

Therefore $I_{n_k}(t, \omega)$ is uniformly convergent for $t \in [0, T]$ for almost all ω . Since $I_n(t, \omega)$ is continuous for all n , the limit, say $J_t(\omega)$, is t -continuous for $t \in [0, T]$ a.s.

For each $t \in [0, T]$,

$$\therefore I_{n_k}(t, \cdot) \xrightarrow{L^2(\mathbb{P})} I(t, \cdot),$$

we must have $\forall t \in [0, T]$

$$I_t = J_t \text{ a.s..}$$

Thus, there exists a t -continuous stochastic process J_t on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ such that

$$\mathbb{P} \left[J_t = \int_0^t f dB \right] = 1 \text{ for all } t; 0 \leq t \leq T$$

□

4.3 One dimensional version of the Itô formula

We now discuss the chain rule of Itô calculus, called the **Itô formula**. Consider a class $W_H(S, T)$ as a class of processes $f(t, \omega) \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfying :

I) $(t, \omega) \rightarrow f(t, \omega)$ is $\mathbb{B} \times \mathcal{F}$ measurable, where \mathbb{B} is the Borel σ -algebra on $[0, \infty)$.

II) There exists an increasing family of σ -algebras $\mathcal{H}_t; t \geq 0$ such that :

- $\{B_t\}_t$ is a martingale with respect to $\{\mathcal{H}_t\}$ and
- $f(t, \omega)$ is \mathcal{H}_t adapted.

III) $\mathbb{P}[\int_S^T f(s, \omega)^2 ds < \infty] = 1$

Define $W_H := \bigcap_{T>0} W_H(0, T)$

Remark 4.3.1. If $f \in W_H$, there exists step functions $f_n \in W_H$ such that

$$\int_0^t |f_n - f|^2 ds \xrightarrow{P} 0$$

for each t .

Then $\int_0^t f(s, \omega) dB_s$ converges in probability to some random variable and the limit only depends on f , not on the sequence $\{f_n\}$. Thus, we define

$$\int_0^t f(s, \omega) dB_s(\omega) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^t f_n(s, \omega) dB_s(\omega) \text{ in probability}$$

for $f \in W_H$

Definition 4.3.2 (Itô processes). [(Øksendal, 1998, Def 4.1.1)] Let $\{B_t\}_t$ be a one-dimensional Brownian Motion on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$. A one-dimensional Itô process is a stochastic process $\{X_t\}_t$ on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ of the form

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t u(s) ds + \int_0^t v(s) dB_s \tag{4.3.1}$$

where $v \in W_H$ and u is \mathcal{H}_t - adapted and

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\int_0^t |u(s, \omega)| ds < \infty \forall t \geq 0 \right] = 1$$

Remark 4.3.3. The relation (3.3.1) is also sometimes written in the shorter differential form :

$$dX_t = udt + vdB_t$$

Theorem 4.3.4 ((Øksendal, 1998, Theorem 4.1.2) The one-dimensional Itô formula).

Let $\{X_t\}_t$ be an Itô process given by

$$dX_t = udt + vdB_t$$

Let $g(t, x)$ be a twice continuously differentiable on $[0, \infty) \times \mathbb{R}$.

Then $Y_t = g(t, X_t)$ is again an Itô process with

$$Y_t = Y_0 + \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial s}(s, X_s) + u(s) \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(s, X_s) + \frac{1}{2} v(s)^2 \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2}(s, X_s) \right) ds + \int_0^t v(s) \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(s, X_s) dB_s.$$

Proof. We may assume that g , $\frac{\partial g}{\partial t}$, $\frac{\partial g}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2}$ are bounded and that $u(t, \omega), v(t, \omega)$ are bounded elementary functions. The general case is then obtained by approximating u and v by bounded elementary functions, as in the construction of the Itô integral. By Taylor's theorem, we get :

$$\begin{aligned} g(t, X_t) &= g(0, X_0) + \sum_j \Delta g(t_j, X_j) \\ &= g(0, X_0) + \sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \Delta t_j + \sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \Delta X_j + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial t \partial x} (\Delta t_j)(\Delta X_j) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} (\Delta X_j)^2 + \sum_j R_j \end{aligned}$$

where $\Delta t_j = t_{j+1} - t_j$, $\Delta X_j = X_{t_{j+1}} - X_{t_j}$, $\Delta g(t_j, X_j) = g(t_{j+1}, X_{t_{j+1}}) - g(t_j, X_{t_j})$ and $R_j = o(|\Delta t_j|^2 + |\Delta X_j|^2)$ for all j .

If $\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \Delta t_j &\rightarrow \int_0^t \frac{\partial g}{\partial t}(s, X_s) ds \\ \sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \Delta X_j &\rightarrow \int_0^t \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(s, X_s) dX_s \end{aligned}$$

Here we use the fact that

$$\sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \Delta X_j = \sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(t_j, X_j)(u(t_j)((t_{j+1} - t_j) + v(t_j)(B_{t_{j+1}} - B_{t_j})))$$

The limit of the first summand turns out to be

$$\sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(t_j, X_j)(u(t_j)(t_{j+1} - t_j)) \xrightarrow{L^2} \int_0^t \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(s, X_s)u(s)ds.$$

Similarly the limit of the second summand

$$\sum_j \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(t_j, X_j)(v(t_j)(B_{t_{j+1}} - B_{t_j}))$$

is $\int_0^t \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}(s, X_s)v(s)ds$.

But u, v are elementary and hence

$$\sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} (\Delta X_j)^2 = \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} u_j^2 (\Delta t_j)^2 + 2 \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} u_j v_j (\Delta t_j) (\Delta B_j) + \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} v_j^2 (\Delta B_j)^2$$

where u_j denotes $u(t_j, \omega)$ and v_j denotes $v(t_j, \omega)$.

Since $\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2}$ and u are bounded, the first two terms go to 0 as $\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$.

Now,

$$E \left[\left(\sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} u_j v_j (\Delta t_j) (\Delta B_j) \right)^2 \right] = E \left[E \left[\left(\sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} u_j v_j (\Delta t_j) (\Delta B_j) \right)^2 \middle| \mathcal{H}_{t_j} \right] \right]$$

Observe that $E[(\Delta B_j)^2 | \mathcal{H}_{t_j}] = t_{j+1} - t_j$ and the expected values of the cross products vanishes. Thus,

$$E \left[E \left[\left(\sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} u_j v_j (\Delta t_j) (\Delta B_j) \right)^2 \middle| \mathcal{H}_{t_j} \right] \right] = \sum_j E \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} u_j v_j \right)^2 (\Delta t_j)^3 \right] \rightarrow 0$$

as $\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$.

We now claim that

$$\sum_j \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} v_j^2 (\Delta B_j)^2 \xrightarrow{L^2(\mathbb{P})} \int_0^t \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} v^2 ds \text{ as } \Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$$

To see this, let $a(t) = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2}(t, X_t)v^2(t, \omega)$, where a_j denotes $a(t_j)$. Here,

$$E \left[\left(\sum_j a_j (\Delta B_j)^2 - \sum_j a_j \Delta t_j \right)^2 \right] = \sum_{i,j} E [a_i a_j ((\Delta B_i)^2 - \Delta t_i) ((\Delta B_j)^2 - \Delta t_j)]$$

If $i \neq j$, $a_i a_j ((\Delta B_i)^2 - \Delta t_i)$ is independent of $(\Delta B_j)^2 - \Delta t_j$. Only contribution comes from the term

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j E[a_j^2 ((\Delta B_j)^2 - \Delta t_j)^2] &= \sum_j E[a_j^2] (3(\Delta t_j)^2 - 2(\Delta t_j)^2 + (\Delta t_j)^2) \\ &= 2 \sum_j E[a_j^2] (\Delta t_j)^2 \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \Delta t_j \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have shown that

$$\sum_j a_j (\Delta B_j)^2 \xrightarrow{L^2(\mathbb{P})} \int_0^t a(s) ds \text{ as } \Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$$

Similarly, we can say by a similar argument that $\sum R_j \rightarrow 0$ as $\Delta t_j \rightarrow 0$. Hence we are done. □

4.3.1 An application of the Itô formula

We now compute the Itô integral in Sec 4.2.1 using the Itô formula. We choose $X_t = B_t$ and observe that $g(t, x) = \frac{x^2}{2}$ is twice continuously differentiable. Then

$$Y_t = \frac{1}{2} B_t^2$$

By Itô's formula,

$$\begin{aligned} dY_t &= \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} dB_t + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} (dB_t)^2 \\ &= B_t dB_t + \frac{1}{2} (dB_t)^2 \\ &= B_t dB_t + \frac{1}{2} dt \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\frac{1}{2} B_t^2 = \int_0^t B_s dB_s + \frac{t}{2} \tag{4.3.2}$$

So, we see that the two expressions of the same integral in (4.3.2) and (4.2.2) agree.

4.4 Existence and Uniqueness Theorem for Stochastic Differential Equations

We are interested in obtaining existence and uniqueness theorems for the differential equation

$$dX_t = b(t, X_t)dt + \sigma(t, X_t)dB_t$$

Theorem 4.4.1 ((Øksendal, 1998, Theorem 5.2.1)). *Let $T > 0$ and*

$$\begin{aligned} b(\cdot, \cdot) &: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \\ \sigma(\cdot, \cdot) &: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \end{aligned}$$

be measurable functions satisfying :

- i) (Linear Growth property) $|b(t, x)| + |\sigma(t, x)| \leq C(1 + |x|)$; $x \in \mathbb{R}^n, t \in [0, T]$ for some constant C , (where $|\sigma|^2 = \sum_{i,j} |\sigma_{ij}|^2$) and
- ii) (Lipschitz continuity) $|b(t, x) - b(t, y)| + |\sigma(t, x) - \sigma(t, y)| \leq D|x - y|$; $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n, t \in [0, T]$ for some constant D .

Let Z be a random variable which is independent of the σ -algebra $\mathcal{F}_\infty^{(m)}$ generated by $B_s(\cdot), s \geq 0$ with $E[|Z|^2] < \infty$. Then the stochastic differential equation

$$dX_t = b(t, X_t)dt + \sigma(t, X_t)dB_t; \quad 0 \leq t \leq T, X_0 = Z$$

has a unique t -continuous solution X_t with the property that

- i) X_t is adapted to the filtration \mathcal{F}_t^Z generated by Z and $B_s(\cdot); s \leq t$ and
- ii) $E[\int_0^T |X_t|^2 dt] < \infty$

Proof. (Proof of uniqueness) : Let $X_1(t, \omega) = X_t(\omega)$ and $X_2(t, \omega) = \hat{X}_t(\omega)$ be solutions with initial values Z, \hat{Z} respectively.

Put

$$\begin{aligned} a(s, \omega) &= b(s, X_s) - b(s, \hat{X}_s) \\ \gamma(s, \omega) &= \sigma(s, X_s) - \sigma(s, \hat{X}_s) \end{aligned}$$

Then, by the Lipschitz continuity of σ and b

$$\begin{aligned} E[|X_t - \hat{X}_t|^2] &= E \left[\left(Z - \hat{Z} + \int_0^t a(s)ds + \int_0^t \gamma(s)dB_s \right)^2 \right] \\ &\leq 3E[|Z - \hat{Z}|^2] + 3E \left[\left(\int_0^t a ds \right)^2 \right] + 3E \left[\left(\int_0^t \gamma dB_s \right)^2 \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq 3E[|Z - \hat{Z}|^2] + 3tE \left[\int_0^t a^2 ds \right] + 3E \left[\int_0^t \gamma^2 ds \right] \\
&\leq 3E[|Z - \hat{Z}|^2] + 3(1+t)D^2 \int_0^t E[|X_s - \hat{X}_s|^2] ds
\end{aligned}$$

We take $v(t) = E[|X_t - \hat{X}_t|^2]$; $0 \leq t \leq T$. It satisfies :

$$v(t) \leq F + A \int_0^t v(s) ds$$

where $F = 3E[|Z - \hat{Z}|^2]$, $A = (1+T)3D^2$.

Using the **Gronwall Inequality**, we have

$$v(t) \leq F \exp(At)$$

Now, assuming $Z = \hat{Z}$, we have $F = 0$ and so $v(t) = 0 \forall t \geq 0$. Hence,

$$P[|X_t - \hat{X}_t| = 0 \forall t \in \mathbb{Q} \cap [0, T]] = 1$$

Using the continuity of $t \rightarrow |X_t - \hat{X}_t|$, it follows that :

$$P[|X_1(t, \omega) - X_2(t, \omega)| = 0, \forall t \in [0, T]] = 1$$

Hence the uniqueness is proved.

(Proof of existence) : We define $Y_t^{(0)} = X_0$ and set $Y_t^{(k)} = Y_t^{(k)}$ inductively as follows:

$$Y_t^{(k+1)} = X_0 + \int_0^t b(s, Y_s^{(k)}) ds + \int_0^t \sigma(s, Y_s^{(k)}) dB_s$$

Then for $k \geq 1, t \leq T$,

$$E[|Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}|^2] \leq (1+T)3D^2 \int_0^t E[|Y_s^{(k)} - Y_s^{(k-1)}|^2] ds$$

for $k = 0$, by the linear growth property of σ and b , we have :

$$E[|Y_t^{(1)} - Y_t^{(0)}|^2] \leq 2C^2 t^2 (1 + E[|X_0|^2]) + 2C^2 t (1 + E[|X_0|^2]) \leq A_1 t$$

where A_1 depends only on C, T and $E|X_0|^2$.

By induction on k , we have :

$$E[|Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}|^2] \leq \frac{A_2^{k+1} t^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} ; k \geq 0, t \in [0, T]$$

where A_2 depends only on C, D, T and $E|X_0|^2$.

Now,

$$\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}| \leq \int_0^T |b(s, Y_s^{(k)}) - b(s, Y_s^{(k-1)})| ds + \sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} \left| \int_0^t \sigma(s, Y_s^{(k)}) - \sigma(s, Y_s^{(k-1)}) dB_s \right|$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} P\left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}| > 2^{-k}\right] &\leq P\left[\left(\int_0^T |b(s, Y_s^{(k)}) - b(s, Y_s^{(k-1)})| ds\right)^2 > 2^{-2k-2}\right] \\ &\quad + P\left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} \left|\int_0^t \sigma(s, Y_s^{(k)}) - \sigma(s, Y_s^{(k-1)}) dB_s\right|^2 > 2^{-k-1}\right] \\ &\leq 2^{2k+2} T \int_0^T E(|b(s, Y_s^{(k)}) - b(s, Y_s^{(k-1)})|^2) ds \\ &\quad + 2^{2k+2} \int_0^T E[|\sigma(s, Y_s^{(k)}) - \sigma(s, Y_s^{(k-1)})|^2] ds \\ &\leq 2^{2k+2} D^2 (T+1) \int_0^T \frac{A_2^k t^k}{k!} dt \\ &\leq \frac{(4A_2 T)^{k+1}}{(k+1)!}, \text{ if } A_2 \geq D^2(T+1) \end{aligned}$$

By Borel-Cantelli Lemma,

$$P\left[\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}| > 2^{-k} \text{ for infinitely many } k\right] = 0$$

Thus, for almost all ω , there exists $k_0 = k_0(\omega)$ such that

$$\sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} |Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}| \leq 2^{-k} \text{ for } k \geq k_0$$

Therefore, $Y_t^{(n)}(\omega) = Y_t^{(0)}(\omega) + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (Y_t^{(k+1)}(\omega) - Y_t^{(k)}(\omega))$ is uniformly convergent in $[0, T]$ for almost all ω .

We denote the limit $X_t = X_t(\omega)$. Then X_t is t -continuous for almost all ω , since $Y_t^{(n)}$ is t -continuous for all n . Again, since $Y_t^{(n)}$ is \mathcal{F}_t^Z measurable for all n , we have $X_t(\cdot)$ is \mathcal{F}_t^Z measurable for all t .

Note that for $m > n \geq 0$, we have :

$$\begin{aligned} E[|Y_t^{(m)} - Y_t^{(n)}|^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} &= \left\| Y_t^{(m)} - Y_t^{(n)} \right\|_{L^2(\mathbb{P})} \\ &= \left\| \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} (Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}) \right\|_{L^2(\mathbb{P})} \\ &\leq \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} \left\| (Y_t^{(k+1)} - Y_t^{(k)}) \right\|_{L^2(\mathbb{P})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{A_2^{k+1} t^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Therefore, $\{Y_t^{(n)}\} \xrightarrow{L^2(\mathbb{P})} Y_t$ (say).

Then, a subsequence of $Y_t^{(n)}(\omega)$ will then converge ω -pointwise to $Y_t(\omega)$ and thus, we must have

$$X_t = Y_t \text{ a.s.}$$

In particular, X_t satisfies (i) and (ii). It remains to show that $\{X_t\}_t$ satisfies the differential equation. For all n , we have

$$Y_t^{(n+1)} = X_0 + \int_0^t b(s, Y_s^{(n)}) ds + \int_0^t \sigma(s, Y_s^{(n)}) dB_s$$

Now, $Y_t^{(n+1)} \rightarrow X_t$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ uniformly in $t \in [0, T]$ for almost all ω . By Fatou's lemma,

$$E\left[\int_0^T |X_t - Y_t^{(n)}|^2 dt\right] \leq \limsup_{m \rightarrow \infty} E\left[\int_0^T |Y_t^{(m)} - Y_t^{(n)}|^2 dt\right] \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Since, $\sigma(t, x)$ is Lipschitz in x ,

$$\sigma(t, Y_t^{(n)}(\omega)) \rightarrow \sigma(t, X_t(\omega)) \text{ in } L^2(\Omega \times [0, T])$$

So, by Itô isometry,

$$\int_0^t \sigma(t, Y_t^{(n)}(\omega)) dB_s \rightarrow \int_0^t \sigma(s, X_s(\omega)) dB_s \text{ in } L^2(\Omega)$$

It also follows from the Hölder inequality that

$$\int_0^t b(s, Y_s^{(n)}) ds \rightarrow \int_0^t b(s, X_s) ds$$

Therefore, taking the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ both sides, we observe that $\{X_t\}_t$ satisfies the stochastic differential equation. □

References

- Klenke, A. (2014). *Probability theory* (Second ed.). Springer, London. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-5361-0> (A comprehensive course) doi: 10.1007/978-1-4471-5361-0
- Mörters, P., & Peres, Y. (2010). *Brownian motion* (Vol. 30). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511750489> (With an appendix by Oded Schramm and Wendelin Werner) doi: 10.1017/CBO9780511750489
- Øksendal, B. (1998). *Stochastic differential equations* (Fifth ed.). Springer-Verlag, Berlin. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-03620-4> (An introduction with applications) doi: 10.1007/978-3-662-03620-4
- Walsh, J. B. (1986). An introduction to stochastic partial differential equations. In *École d'été de probabilités de Saint-Flour, XIV—1984* (Vol. 1180, pp. 265–439). Springer, Berlin. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/BFb0074920> doi: 10.1007/BFb0074920